

Integrated pest management — weeds

Weed control in wet seeded rice (WSR) in Bangladesh

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Farmers in Bangladesh generally cultivate boro (dry season irrigated) rice as a transplanted crop. Uprooting and subsequent transplanting of seedlings are labor-intensive. Transplanting shock also increases crop growth duration. Rice sown as pregerminated seed on puddled soil and irrigated a few days later has outyielded transplanted rice in many rice-producing countries.

We conducted trials at BRRI, Joydebpur, during boro season to determine WSR performance with regard to weed components and labor requirements for weeding.

Treatments were two planting methods, direct seeding and transplanting, and three weed control methods: hand weeding, herbicidal control with oxadiazon at 0.5 kg ai/ha, and no weed control. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications. Plots were 4 m².

We transplanted 48-d-old BR14 seedlings on 25 Jan 1990 and 58-d-old seedlings on 6 Feb 1991 at 20- x 20-cm spacing. Pregerminated seeds were broadcast on the same days. Seed rates were 45 kg/ha for transplanting and 90 kg/ha for wet seeding. Irrigation water was applied when necessary. Plots were weeded at 20 and 40 d after planting (DP) in both years. Herbicide was applied at 7 DP.

Fertilizer was applied at 80-26-33-40 kg NPKS/ha as urea, triple superphosphate (TSP), muriate of potash (MP), and gypsum. One-third urea, all TSP, MP, and gypsum were basally applied before planting. The rest of the urea was applied in two equal splits at active tillering and panicle initiation stages. An extra 13 kg P/ha was applied at 54 DP in 1990 because of P deficiency. Carbofuran at 15 kg/ha was applied at maximum tillering to control stem borers.

Grain yield of boro rice and labor requirements as influenced by cultivation methods.^a

Cultivation method	Weed control method	Weed density (no./m ²)		Weed weight (g/m ²)		Labor and seed costs ^b (\$/ha)				Grain yield (t/ha)	
		1990	1991	1990	1991	Weeding/spray		Total production costs ^c		1990	1991
						1990	1991	1990	1991		
Transplanting	Hand	176 a	361 a	56.3 a	54.5 a	72	67	147	138	3.5 a	3.7 a
Direct sowing	Hand	153 a	438 a	68.3 a	56.3 a	117	111	144	139	3.7 a	3.4 a
Transplanting	Herbicide	—	—	—	—	2	1.5	76	74	3.3 a	3.5 a
Direct sowing	Herbicide	—	—	—	—	2	1.5	30	29	3.8 a	3.5 a
Transplanting	None	296 b	412 a	298.2 b	158.1 c	—	—	72	72	2.2 b	2.2 b
Direct sowing	None	312 b	576 a	311.9 b	146.6 b	—	—	26	26	2.3 b	2.4 b
	CV (%)	6.5	12.2	28.5	1.7					10.0	7.1

^a Letters in a column compare means at P_{0.05} level by Duncan's multiple range test. ^b Labor cost @ \$1.025/person-day; seed cost @ \$0.269/kg. ^c Labor required for seedling uprooting, transplanting/sowing, herbicide spraying, and hand weeding; includes seed cost.

Labor required for seedling uprooting, transplanting or sowing, herbicide spraying, and weeding was recorded. Weeds from 1 m² were collected prior to weeding, cleaned, and densities determined. Weed dry weights were recorded after oven-drying at 70°C for 72 h. Grain yields from the whole plot were recorded and adjusted to 14% moisture content.

Cynodon dactylon, *Fimbristylis miliacea*, *Marsilea crenata*, *Monochoria vaginalis*, *Cyperus difformis*, *Anagallis arvensis*, and *Scirpus mucronatus* were the dominant weed species.

Weed density and weed weight in 1990 were higher in WSR and TPR

weedy check than in the other treatments (see table). Cost of hand weeding in WSR was about twice as much as for transplanted rice. Production costs were similar in both systems (see table). A similar trend was observed in 1991, but there was no significant difference in weed density.

Crop establishment techniques produced no significant yield difference in 1990 (see table). Though the unweeded check had the lowest grain yield, the mean grain yield did not vary because of methods of crop establishment and weed control.

Boro rice can be cultivated as WSR. □

Farming systems

Particle boards from paddy straw

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Rice straw is a cheap, readily available material in rice-growing areas. It is sometimes used as cattle feed or roof thatch, or is returned to the soil. Most rice straw, however, is simply wasted; it is thrown on roads or burned.

We studied an alternative: using

rice straw as the basic raw material for particle boards.

Dry straw was cut into small pieces, finely ground using a commercial grinder, and then sieved. Uniform-sized particles were blended with resin and a hardener. It was then molded into a board and oven-dried under pressure at 45-50°C for 5-6 h. Particle boards were cooled and then subjected to quality tests.

Results indicate that rice straw can be used to produce particle boards that conform to several Indian standards (No. IS-3129/1965, IS-3087/1965, and IS-3478/1966 [see table]).

Rice straw can be used to make soft and hard boards, insulation (for low